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“The Transdisciplinarity of the Social Sciences and Humanities as Potential for Solving Complex Problems in the Scientific Context”

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Paper presented at the International Conference:

The Role of Social Sciences and Humanities in Socio-Economic Development and International Integration

Conference held at Vietnam National University in Ho Chi Minh City-University of Social Sciences & Humanities, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

November, 19th-22nd 2017

Organised by:

Vietnam National University in Ho Chi Minh City-University of Social Sciences & Humanities

Thu Dau Mot University

People’s Committee of Binh Duong Province

Citation:

Sánchez-Escobar, F. (2017). *The Transdisciplinarity of the Social Sciences and Humanities as Potential for Solving Complex Problems in the Scientific Context*. Paper presented at the International Conference on The Role of Social Sciences and Humanities in Socio-Economic Development and International Integration, November 19th-22nd. Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam: VNUCHM, University of Social Sciences and Humanities.

Title:

“The transdisciplinarity of the social sciences and humanities as potential for solving complex problems in the scientific context”

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Abstract:

As human societies have advanced in the last century, new disciplines have emerged in the field of knowledge to respond to the problems associated with their evolution. This phenomenon has affected the natural sciences, social sciences and humanities. In this context, the scientific problems have traditionally been approached from a disciplinary approach. This has been reflected in the composition of the studies in the Universities and the orientation of the research centres in the world. However, since the beginning of the 21st century, the emergence of new paradigms and conceptual approaches has been experienced to solve complex problems that could not be solved from traditional approaches. These new paradigms are related to transdisciplinarity and complexity, and fundamentally consist in the development of a holistic vision in the field of knowledge. This paper examines the role that social science and humanities studies can play in developing transdisciplinary approaches to solving complex scientific problems that need to be addressed from broad perspectives. Likewise, it also analyse the difficulties of higher education institutions and research institutes for their adaptation to the transdisciplinary approach.

Keywords: transdisciplinarity; complexity; higher education; paradigm.

Introduction

Universities and research centers play a fundamental role in understanding reality through the generation of knowledge. These institutions have developed knowledge with the objective of solving the problems that concern human societies. However, the way to carry out it has evolved through history, therefore humanities, social sciences, and natural sciences have experienced a series of changes over time. Thus, from the Renaissance, *humanism* began to spread in the universities as a logic to understand reality, which was a new form of thinking that broke the monopoly of the *scholastic* tradition that had dominated Western thought in learning centers (Black, 2007), although it still continued to playing a major role in European universities during that period (Hankins, 2007). With the advent of this way of thinking, the center of knowledge

passed from theocentrism and metaphysics to anthropocentrism, which will influence up to the present in the ways of generating knowledge in institutions of higher education.

The historical evolution of scientific thinking has influenced the organization of higher education in the world. Countries have shaped universities and colleges in accordance with the dominant scientific paradigms in the world. In this sense, knowledge of these is essential to understand the current division between humanities, social and natural sciences (Scott, 2006). However, there are currently authors who consider that the current knowledge system and its institutional organization does not provide adequate answers to solve the complex problems that currently affect modern societies (Amaral & Magalhães, 2003; Batty, 1988; Blumenstyk, 2015; Boidin, Cohen, & Grosfoguel, 2012; Giroux, 2009; Maldonado-Torres, 2011; Radice, 2013; Shin, 2014).

The objectives of this article are, firstly, to offer a brief description of the main paradigms that influence the configuration of the modern university from a historical perspective, second, to present a vision of the problems associated with this configuration and, finally, to propose paradigmatic solutions focused on another way of conceiving knowledge. In particular, the proposed solution focuses on the theoretical approach of transdisciplinarity (Nicolescu, 2010). Furthermore, within this approach, I analyse the new role that the humanities will carry out in this new way of viewing knowledge, in addition to the implications that may have for scientific and non-scientific knowledge.

The configuration of the modern university: the disciplinarity of knowledge

With the advent of the Early Modern Period, a definitive break with the scholastic tradition took place in European universities. Thus, Bacon in 1620 (Bacon, 1620/1889) laid the foundations of empiricism as a way of approaching reality. This favoured the development of physics, chemistry, biology and other disciplines related to the exact sciences, which assumed the *baconian* methods of observation (Klein, 2016) as the cornerstone in the construction of knowledge.

In the second half of the eighteenth century, Hume (1739/1888) consolidated empiricism at the same time as philosophical ideas of *newtonian determinism* and *cartesian dualism* were assumed by the Enlightenment as a form of knowledge of reality. From this perspective, reality was governed by natural laws which therefore operated in a mechanical, deterministic and *newtonian* way. These laws could and should be discovered through the application of scientific method based on experimentation and reason (Hazony & Schliesser, 2016).

This form of philosophical thought spread throughout all branches of knowledge, including the social sciences, which tried to follow *physicalism*, that is, trying to imitate physics as an ideal of science. In the mid-nineteenth century, August Comte, influenced

by Hume's empiricism, developed positivism as a way of proceeding in science, for which reason the quest for the original causes of things was finally given up (Bourdeau, 2015). The scientist would no longer raise the question of why events occurred in the world, but rather would focus on how. This should be done through the formulation of the laws of nature which, at the same time, should be expressed in a formal language. The great contribution of Comte was to apply this to social phenomena, conceiving sociology as a social physics (Robbins, 2017).

If the Enlightenment established the positivist philosophical bases for the understanding of reality, the second Industrial Revolution contributed to its expansion and the development of new fields of knowledge, which gave rise to disciplinarity (Kreber, 2008). This had important implications for the organization of higher education. In the 19th century, universities became central institutions for the development of nations and the diffusion of national ideologies (Altbach, 2008). In Europe, the German universities, created by Von Humboldt, were expanded or supplemented with colleges or polytechnic schools which were elevated to the category of technological universities with the support of the Nation-States (Nybom, 2007). In this way, *humanism* was transformed from the University model of the modern period to *neo-humanism* in the modern University. The latter, unlike the previous one, focused on scientific and technical knowledge, and added the research role to the University (Scott, 2006). Following this trend, the United States government granted in 1862 aid for the construction of American universities with the aim of contributing to the Industrial Revolution. This is the case of the creation of MIT in 1865. Similarly, in Asia the same tendency is experienced in Japan with the process of industrialization of the Meiji restoration of 1868, which created the imperial universities in Japan with the mission of contributing to the industrial development of the nation (Altbach, 2008).

Economic development and *entrepreneurial* university

During the 20th century, this model expanded throughout the rest of the world, and a third function, economic growth, was added to the previous two of research and teaching (Geuna & Rossi, 2015; Labini, 2015). From that time on, universities will play an important role in the economic growth and well-being of the population. After World War II, during *fordism* (Jessop, 1992), university expanded into developed and developing countries and there was a symbiosis between university and State with the aim of extending economic development in the various sectors and improve the welfare of broad strata of the population. Thus, universities became public institutions that provided society with roadmaps for economic development in a mass-production environment (Murphy, 2015).

However, the crisis of *fordism* (Jessop, 1996) brought about a change in the organization of higher education institutions towards the idea of *entrepreneurial university* (Jessop,

2017), that is, the transformation of higher education into a kind of business whose objectives were to make money in the market through the activities of investigation and education (Derek, 2003; Olssen & Peters, 2005; Sam & van der Sijde, 2014). From a less critical perspective, institutionalists (Corbett, 2005; Diogo, Carvalho, & Amaral, 2015) consider *entrepreneurial university* as an organization formed by networks of academic and non-academic actors that aim at creating value by developing the characteristic features of an innovative entrepreneur.

In this way, a new *post-fordist* regulatory framework (Jessop, 1996), characterized by the reduction of the state in the capitalist system, was transferred to the university through budget reductions, research cuts and privatizations (Amaral & Magalhães, 2003; Batty, 1988; Blumenstyk, 2015; Giroux, 2009; Meyer, John, Chankseliani, & Uribe, 2013), which implied social problems related to social exclusion and discontent (Belina, Petzold, Schardt, & Schipper, 2013; Giroux, 2002).

From an institutionalist perspective, the university adapted to a new global and more competitive framework characterized by internationalization, the emergence of new players, such as spin-offs, university-industry innovation networks, where the research component is considered the main success factor of the university (Altbach, Reisberg, & Rumbley, 2009; Evers, Cunningham, & Hoholm, 2016). In this context, the university of international success appeared, focused on research, competitive and able to attract students and research funds worldwide. However, not all universities were able to make this transformation, as the fundraising capacity for research was concentrated in the most excellent institutions, which are evaluated by the international rankings (Liu, 2015; Pusser & Marginson, 2013; Taylor & Braddock, 2007). Thus, the top universities in the rankings are more competitive and monopolize most of the resources for research. In addition, not all universities have the same adaptive capabilities. Therefore, those in developed countries are better positioned than those located in developing countries (Altbach 2013, p. 324) because they have extensive research trajectories, greater institutional and economic support from governments and companies, which is reflected in infrastructures and research equipment. Furthermore, within these countries, the top tend to be a minority of the total, such as Harvard, Oxford, MIT, Berkeley, etc., implying a existence of winner and loser universities and disciplines (Amsler & Bolsmann, 2012; Collyer, 2013), which opens the debate about the appropriateness of this type of rankings to evaluate universities (Hallinger, 2014; Kehm, 2014; Lynch, 2015).

Specialization of the university and complex problems

In this context, new aspects arise that reformulate the concept of modern university of the present defined since the reform of von Humboldt in the nineteenth century, the *entrepreneurial university* (Sam & van der Sijde, 2014) and the university of excellence in research (Altbach, 2011). On the one hand, knowledge has expanded enormously from the late nineteenth century to the present, which has led to the emergence of an infinity of disciplines (Jacobs, 2017). On the other, these disciplines have specialized the university and configured specific departments and forms of teaching that make it difficult to introduce innovations into the knowledge system (Kreber, 2008).

In addition, traditional forms of knowledge (popular knowledge, indigenous, ethnic traditions, etc.) have been eliminated in the configuration of the disciplines or have been relegated to very specific disciplines related to cultural anthropology. This makes it difficult to integrate forms of local knowledge, traditional knowledge and minority studies into the political agenda of the disciplinary knowledge structure, such as ethnic and racial studies, migrations or critical approaches to development (Boatcă, 2012; Maldonado-Torres, 2011).

This is due, on the one hand, to a reduced vision of the humanities, which follows the disciplinary tradition inherited from the modern university, at the same time as difficulties in integrating this type of knowledge into its structure of teaching and research. On the other hand, it is also due to the subordination of the humanities to the preponderance of scientific-technological knowledge in research programs, since the *post-Fordist* framework promotes *instrumental knowledge* (Habermas, 1968/2015) related to *entrepreneurial university*. This *instrumental knowledge* has allowed the development of contemporary modern societies, whose maximal exponent is industrialization and development, within the framework of a socioecological system dominated by the industrial *sociometabolic regime* (M Fischer-Kowalski, Krausmann, & Pallua, 2014). But this development is also the cause of serious global problems that affect the world today, such as climate change, global warming, habitat contamination, massive destruction of species, demographic crisis or loss of cultures (Ammarell, 2014; Barnosky et al., 2014) whose impacts have suggested a new way of naming the geological epoch in which we live, the *Anthropocene* (Crutzen, 2006; Lewis & Maslin, 2015).

All these problems have a high level of complexity. In this sense, the socioecological system is characterized by a system of interrelations between social and natural systems that owes its existence to social and natural processes, and which can only be understood by the existence of a set of interactions (Bodin & Tengö, 2012). If the problem can only be understood in a holistic way, the traditional disciplinary division that separates the social sciences from the natural sciences is not capable of responding in a satisfactory

way to understanding the problems associated with the complexity of the present world. This means the boundaries delimited by traditional disciplines must be overcome in a joint way involving the entire society, both scientific and non-scientific actors (Seidl et al., 2013). In this way, the *cartesian-dualist* tradition that divides the separation of knowledge into disciplines is overcome, but also the *newtonian* way of thinking that links knowledge to linear and mechanical processes that can be predicted through empiricism (McGregor, 2014).

The solution to achieve this goal is transdisciplinarity, but it must be understood in a broad sense, not only in a practical sense with the participation of scientific and non-scientific actors (Lang et al., 2012). In particular, it must be focused in an epistemological and ontological sense that is not exempt from principles and values (Nicolescu, 2014). But first of all, it should be noted that the introduction of principles and values in the scheme to be proposed gives the humanities an essential role in the conceptualization of knowledge for the resolution of the complex problems that affect humanity. This role should be developed and incorporated into institutions of higher education as key actors in the generation of knowledge. The next section describes the proposed approach to solving complex problems in the field of knowledge generation.

The approach of transdisciplinarity and complexity

The approach adopted in this paper focuses on a conceptual scheme developed from two basic ideas. On the one hand, transdisciplinarity, for which the epistemological perspective of Nicolescu (1996, 2005, 2010, 2014) is followed. On the other hand, since transdisciplinarity aims to give a coherent answer to the complex problems of the world at the present time, it is necessary to introduce some ideas related to complexity (Preiser & Cillier, 2010). With respect to the first, Nicolescu (1996, 2010) conceives the epistemology of transdisciplinarity based on three fundamental axioms:

- 1) Ontological axiom: in nature and in society, as well as in their knowledge, there are different levels of reality in which a set of laws are manifested (to be interpreted as properties, tendencies and processes, and not in the *humean* sense of law). When one passes from one level to another, there is a discontinuity that manifests itself in a rupture in the application of the laws that govern them and, therefore, of fundamental principles such as that of causality. The coexistence of several levels associated with a given dimension implies the presence of a structured multidimensional and multireferential reality, in which the laws that govern each level are a part of the totality of laws that act at all levels (Nicolescu 2010, pp. 22-23). Likewise, the levels of reality are incomplete, in the terminology of Nicolescu, because constantly new laws can be manifested, which produces a break with *newtonian* determinism.

- 2) Logical axiom: the passage from one level to another is ensured by the logic of the inclusion of the third term. This principle is related to the existence of contradiction in reality, which in the case of positivism was solved by denying its rationality through the postulates of logic, and more specifically by the exclusion of the third term, according to the classical laws of thought (Russell, 1912). However, these postulates were not able to explain the existence of the principle of superposition in quantum physics, which an object can simultaneously manifest two or more observable values (Nicolescu 2010, p. 26), nor to reveal the contradictions existing in the social systems. On the contrary, the inclusion of the third term allows the justification of the simultaneous existence of a phenomenon and its opposite through a triangular relationship. In addition, the third term can be located in the vertex corresponding to a different level of reality. The application of this logic allows us to contemplate the relations of unity in what is apparently disunited, so that what was observed as contradictory is now perceived as not incompatible (p. 26). In this way, the inclusion of the third term is a tool to integrate coherently different levels of reality, both in relation to knowledge and being (p. 27).
- 3) Axiom of complexity. The totality of reality levels and its perception is conceived as a complex structure: the existence of one level is explained by the presence of another. It is also necessary to distinguish between horizontal complexity, which refers to a simple level of reality, and vertical complexity, which alludes to various levels of reality. This vision connects with Morin's generalized complexity approach (Morin, 2007), which, as Nicolescu (2010, p. 27) points out, goes beyond a systemic approach because it is not reduced to formal language (though not excluded). Rather, this vision adopts a symbolic language that allows us to grasp in a more comprehensive way the elements related to certain levels of reality, such as the issues associated with human thought, ideas, feelings and emotions. All of these guide human behavior and, therefore, have indirect consequences on the rest of the whole.

These three interrelated axioms will give us the general view of transdisciplinarity. But one of these three, the axiom of complexity, is the pillar where lies the importance of the humanities in the understanding of reality, which we can only contemplate through our thought, principles and values. Moreover, when we select the part of reality that we want to understand, we are making a value judgment because we leave out of the analysis other parts of reality, which at the same time influence what we want to analyse. In this way, the humanities become the lens from which we observe reality. Therefore, knowing the lens will help us to make better interpretations of reality.

The conceptualization described can be seen as an epistemology that offers a general view of the systemic but, above all, holistic reality, without eliminating the parts of the

whole, which contributes, at the same time, to overcoming the anthropocentric vision from a perspective of biocentric reality. Also, transdisciplinarity is conceived as something consubstantial to complexity since both are united by the third axiom in a mutual and bidirectional relationship that gives rise to an essential theoretical tool to approach the understanding of reality where the humanities will play a vital role (Montuori, 2013).

To clarify the relationship between humanities, transdisciplinarity and complexity, it is necessary to introduce two basic ideas about the latter concept. In relation to the first, complexity assumes an ontology that recognizes the existence of a reality that is impossible to encompass and, therefore, can only be accessed through reductionist methods (Cilliers, 2005). The description of this type of generalized complexity cannot be grasped through the use of a single language, but rather a plurality of descriptions of reality articulated through a transdisciplinary vision covering non-formal languages, especially in relation to social systems (Cilliers & Preiser 2010, p. vi). In this way, the incorporation of these two types of languages surpasses the holistic and reductionist vision and, consequently, the *cartesian dualism* that has characterized the knowledge since the Early Modern Period, which implies a qualitative leap in human thought.

In relation to the second idea, it is necessary to consider an important aspect regarding the choice of method as the interpretation of results. Specifically, scientific knowledge is not exempt from the values and interests of the social groups involved (Kunneman 2010, p. 134). Discourses are fundamental in the generation and interpretation of knowledge, and these will depend on the social groups that dominate societies through power relations (Foucault, 1980, 1982). Thus, the relationships of the socioecological system will be influenced by power relations (Marina Fischer-Kowalski, 2011). As a consequence, universities and research centres will tend to seek solutions to problems in line with these relationships. In this sense, modern research and entrepreneurial universities that are positioned at the top of the rankings will have more resources and facilities to find solutions to current problems.

However, if the cause of current problems is mainly due to the evolution of modern societies in the industrial socio-ecological system, the resolution of these problems will require the overcoming of the paradigms of the dominant currents in the centers of knowledge¹. For example, when we are faced with complex issues such as the sustainability and unsustainability of human society, then we will have to question values, assumptions, and normative aspects through a reflexive science (Popa, Guillermin, & Dedeurwaerdere, 2015). In relation to this, according to Klein (2014), the approach of transdisciplinarity and complexity contributes to the generation of three

¹ In relation to this, Kuhn (1962) expounded in the 1960s that modern science, dominated by positivism, was in crisis and that the solution would come through a scientific revolution that changes the paradigms.

types of discourses, overlapping each other, in particular, related to transcendence, problem solving, and transgression. In this way, this approach aligns with cultural criticism and a reflexive science open to paradigm shift. This facilitates the incorporation of traditional knowledge, gender, ethnic studies and all kinds of minority studies that traditionally have been underestimated in the national scientific programs of institutions of higher education, in scientific knowledge (Meranze, 2015). Consequently, this approach is the gateway for scientific programs to reconsider the humanities as a source for resolving the complex problems of the modern world.

Conclusions

The approach of transdisciplinarity contributes to overcoming the dilemma of *cartesian dualism* and *newtonian mechanicism* that has characterized knowledge since the Early Modern Period. The underlying ontological framework of transdisciplinarity recognizes that reality is multicausal, multidimensional, and breaks the *baconian* and *humean* approach to knowledge. However, this should not be considered as a confrontation with the positivist tradition, but rather positivism must be integrated into the scheme of complexity as a tool for understanding reality, subject to principles, values and rules that guide the interpretation of reality. The humanities will contribute to the choice, change or modification of principles, norms and values, according to ethical and metaphysical approaches that will allow modern societies to improve the understanding of reality and, as a consequence, the solution of complex problems.

This has important implications for designing knowledge divisions, universities and research centres. If the present university crisis is related to the inability to solve problems in the current societies of the industrial socio-ecological system (Fischer-Kowalski, 2011), it is necessary to redesign these institutions in order that they can better connect with the problems of current world. Until now, the organization of knowledge in the university has followed the traditional division of disciplines grouped by departments or faculties. However, from a transdisciplinary perspective, the organization of knowledge should transcend this division and focus rather on responding to questions about what are the major issues affecting society and how we can solve them (Graff, 2015; McGregor, 2014; McGregor & Volckmann, 2013). This is a major challenge for the humanities, although is difficult to reach because of the weight of current ranking systems, where entrepreneurial and research universities are better situated (Frodeman, 2017).

Finally, despite the difficulties involved in these changes, the resolution of complex problems will only be possible to the extent that the principles and values that guide universities and modern research centres in the current socio-ecological system change. These changes will depend on the ability and willingness of modern societies to make this transition. The search for solutions in other non-Western philosophical traditions

(e.g. Confucianism, Buddhist, Hindu, etc.), particularly Asian ones, will contribute to the search for solutions. In this sense, universities located in countries with non-Western traditions will play a key role in recognizing these forms of knowledge as a means of addressing complex problems.

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